

Deactivation of zeolite catalyst in aniline alkylation

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Deactivation of zeolite used in aniline alkylation by 2-propanol in vapour phase under atmospheric pressure has been investigated. Blockage of pores and coverage of surface of zeolite by carbonaceous materials and poisoning of active sites by nitrogenous compounds are causes of deactivation. The coke deposit is more in Ce-form than that in Na-form. This is attributed to the relatively higher acidity of Ce-Y form. Deactivated catalyst is regenerated by heating it in a current of air at 500° for 8 h. Regenerated catalyst shows improved activity.

Deactivation of catalyst due to the accumulation of carbonaceous deposits on the catalyst surface is a phenomenon of considerable importance in industrial practice. Coking as a cause of deactivation is still not fully understood. Deactivation of ZSM-5 by coke formation during organic reactions was reported¹. The pore structure of ZSM-5 does not allow transport of poisons that neutralize Bronsted acid sites². Groten *et al.*³ studied the formation of coke and other products in the catalytic cracking of n-hexane on USHY-zeolite. The deactivation of ZSM-5 in catalytic dewaxing was investigated by Chen *et al.*⁴. Coke formation and deactivation of zeolite HY and Pt-H-mordenite catalysts during hydrogenation of benzene was reported⁵. The characterisation methods, coke forms, mechanism for coke formation and location of coke zeolite have been widely studied⁶. Pitkanen and Keane⁷ reported catalyst deactivation in the alkylation of xylene with methanol using Y-zeolite. Coking and regeneration of zeolite catalyst in fixed bed during cumene cracking was investigated by Acharya *et al.*⁸. The effect of hydrothermal treatment of Y-zeolite on coke formation was studied⁹. A detailed review on deactivation of zeolite was reported by Guisnet and Magnoux¹⁰. Mori and Nishiyama¹¹ studied deactivation of H-type zeolites (H-mordenite, H-Y and HZSM-5) in n-hexane cracking. Excellent reports have been made correlating coking and deactivation with acidic, structural and other properties of the zeolites¹². But no effort has been made to study the deactivation mechanism of alkylation of aniline. Deactivation of oxide catalyst during alkylation of aniline was reported early from our laboratory¹³. In continuation of aniline alkylation over oxide catalyst¹⁴, we reported synthesis of secondary amines over zeolite¹⁵. The purpose of the present study is to find the longevity, causes of deactivation of zeolite of different activity used in the alkylation of aniline with 2-propanol in vapour phase at atmospheric pressure.

Results and Discussion

The results of the reaction of aniline with 2-propanol over NaY-zeolite are listed in Table 1. Reactions were performed at 400° at a flow rate of 5 ml h⁻¹. The reaction was carried for 15 h continuously. The product samples were collected at the end of the each hour. At the end of 60 min, the conversion was 33.3 mole %. It was almost constant for first 6 h. It is clear that the zeolite catalysts did not suffer much deactivation during usage for a period of upto 6 h.

Table 1. Study on stability of Na-Y zeolite used in alkylation of aniline with 2-propanol

Wt. of catalyst = 7 g, Temp. = 400°, Flow rate = 5 ml h⁻¹,
aniline : IPA = 1 : 3 (mole)

Time on stream h	Mole % conversion of aniline	%Selectivity of products*		
		A	B	C
1	33.3	73.1	20.6	6.3
2	33.2	73.2	20.4	6.4
3	33.6	72.8	20.1	7.1
4	33.1	73.0	20.3	7.7
5	33.2	73.1	19.1	8.8
6	33.0	73.4	18.0	8.6
7	32.1	74.0	16.7	9.3
8	31.0	75.1	16.2	8.7
9	29.2	76.3	15.3	8.4
10	27.0	77.2	14.8	8.0
11	26.0	81.2	10.9	7.9
12	24.0	83.1	10.7	6.2
13	20.3	86.2	9.0	4.8
14	11.8	88.0	8.3	3.7
15	8.0	90.0	7.7	1.3
Regenerated catalyst	29.7	75.3	21.6	3.1

*A = *N*-Isopropylaniline; B = *o*-isopropylaniline; C = *p*-isopropylaniline.

From the 7th hour onwards the conversion of aniline decreased to 8.0 at 15th hour. A major step in the formation of carbonaceous residues is the reaction and conversion of alkylaromatics by cyclisation, dehydrogenation, further alkylation etc. leading to polyalkyl aromatics and polyaromatics which are coke precursors. Coke deposition which poisons the acid sites of the catalyst as well as blocks the pores, is the main reason for catalyst deactivation in gas phase organic reaction.

The catalyst deactivation can result from poisoning, from fouling or from sintering. Once the catalyst is deactivated the coke continues to migrate over the surface of catalyst. The deactivation of zeolite is definitely due to the blockage by the coke molecules deposited in the large channels of catalyst. The foulant, coke deposited on the catalyst, can be removed to regenerate the catalyst. Sintering on the other hand, is largely irreversible and necessitates replacement of the catalyst. A single coke molecule is sufficient to block the access of the reactant. Therefore the deactivating effect of coke is very significant. It is now well known that the rate of coking, the composition of coke and its deactivation depend on the zeolite pore structure, on the acidity and the operating conditions such as temperature, flow rate etc.

The amount of coke present in the deactivated catalyst was estimated by gravimetric and thermal analyses. The activity of Ce-Y zeolite used in the alkylation of aniline with isopropylalcohol was studied (Table 2). The activity of the catalyst was 57.3 in the first hour, remained almost constant for 6 h and from 7th hour onwards it decreased gradually to 12.1 at the end of 15th hour. Relative to Na-form of zeolite, the deactivation was higher in Ce-Y zeolite. It is reported that coke formation is higher in the more acidic form of zeolite. The higher rate of deactivation in Ce-Y can be anticipated to poisoning of catalyst by nitrogenous organic compound which can be coordinately form compounds with acid sites of the zeolite catalyst. More the acidity of the zeolite, greater is the chance of forming the coordinated compound. The temperature rise observed during the regeneration of Ce-Y zeolite was higher than that in the case of Na-form. It is well established that temperature attained during regeneration is proportional to the coke present. It can be seen that as the amount of coke increases in the bed, higher temperature rise is obtained. The amount of coke, loss in acidity and pore volume of coked samples suggest that deactivation of Ce-Y is mainly due to acid-site poisoning.

In a parallel reaction, the isopropyl alcohol over zeolite gives propene which on polymerisation produces coke. The formation of coke from propene can also contribute for the

Table 2. Study on stability of Ce-Y zeolite used in alkylation of aniline with 2-propanol

Wt. of catalyst = 7 g, Temp. = 400°, Flow rate = 5 ml h⁻¹, aniline : IPA = 1 : 3 (mole)

Time on stream h	Mole % conversion of aniline	% Selectivity of products*			
		A	B	C	D
1	57.3	62.7	24.3	8.7	4.3
2	57.4	62.4	24.2	9.2	4.2
3	57.2	62.8	24.0	9.2	4.0
4	56.9	64.7	21.7	9.7	3.9
5	57.1	66.2	22.2	9.5	2.1
6	55.7	70.5	19.0	8.5	2.0
7	53.3	71.3	19.1	7.7	1.9
8	48.0	73.2	18.2	7.1	1.5
9	42.7	76.3	16.6	6.0	1.1
10	31.5	78.6	16.1	4.0	1.3
11	24.3	82.0	13.5	4.5	-
12	19.2	83.0	13.1	3.9	-
13	17.1	84.3	12.7	3.0	-
14	13.2	85.2	11.8	3.0	-
15	12.1	85.3	12.0	2.7	-
Regenerated catalyst	51.4	63.0	21.2	11.8	4.0

*A = *N*-Isopropylaniline; B = *o*-isopropylaniline; C = *p*-isopropylaniline, D = dialkylated products.

deactivation of the catalyst.

Determination of coke deposited on the catalyst : The coke formation during the reaction was determined by heating the deactivated catalyst at 500° for 6 h in a current of air. The weight of carbon was determined by estimating the CO₂ evolved by barium hydroxide method. The coke formation was maximum on Ce-Y catalyst (Na-Y, 18.1%; Ce-Y, 23.2% carbon).

The results of thermogravimetric analysis of the fresh, deactivated and regenerated catalyst are presented in Table 3. The loss of weight in the fresh catalyst is due to the en-

Table 3. Comparative account of activity with surface area

Catalyst	Surface area m ² g ⁻¹	Activity	% Wt.-loss (TGA)
Na-Y fresh	332	33.3	20.3
Na-Y used	265	9.8	18.7
Na-Y regenerated	309	29.7	Nil
Ce-Y fresh	351	56.3	21.7
Ce-Y used	276	13.2	23.6
Ce-Y regenerated	334	51.3	Nil

capsuled water molecules. The loss of weight in the used catalyst is because of the nitrogenous compounds and carbonaceous materials formed in the catalyst.

Experimental

Y-zeolites (Union Carbide) were converted to cation form by the standard procedures. The catalyst (7 g) was taken in a pyrex glass reactor (2.5 cm dia × 40 cm) kept in a cylindrical furnace and the space above the catalyst was packed with pyrex glass beads, which acted as a preheated zone. The catalyst was used without binder. The surface area of the fresh Na-Y was 322 and that of Ce-Y 351 m² g⁻¹. The extent of ion exchange Na to Ce was 87% which was determined by inductively coupled plasma technique. The catalyst was activated at 500° for 4 h before the longevity study. Thereafter, the temperature was brought down to the reaction temperature in a stream of pure dry nitrogen. The liquid mixture was introduced at the top of the reactor by means of an infusion pump. The products passed through a water-cooled condenser and collected in an ice-cooled receiver. The liquid products obtained were analysed by capillary gas chromatography using 5 m methylsilicon gum column, temperature programmed 30–220° at the rate of 10°/min using nitrogen as carrier gas, and GC-MS using 50 m FFAP column programmed 100–220° at the rate of 3°/min using nitrogen as carrier gas.

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